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Explaining cross-country variation in timing and work exit routes among older workers

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PATHS2INCLUDE

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**European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations**

Title: Explaining cross-country variation in timing and work exit routes among older workers

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Introduction

This working paper is part of PATHS2INCLUDE, a research project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe (101094626). The overall objective of PATHS2INCLUDE is to disentangle the dimensions of discrimination and unequal opportunities in the labour market to gain knowledge on how to develop inclusive labour markets for persons in vulnerable situations. A key goal is to understand how contextual factors disproportionately expose certain groups to risk and vulnerability throughout their life course and during critical transitions. This working paper is part of Work Package 5, with the overarching goal to study employment policies and institutional and individual factors affecting employment among older workers.

This working paper focuses on exiting the labour market as one of the critical transitions people go through during their life. The aim of this working paper is twofold: first, to provide an overview of recent research examining individual risk factors, such as gender, health limitations, care responsibilities, and income poverty, that may influence the timing of exit and work exit routes for older workers. Second, to employ descriptive analyses to examine whether the individual factors influence older workers' intention to retire and their different pathways out of the workforce, and how these factors overlap and may placing individuals with such characteristics in vulnerable situations.

The working paper is organised into three main parts: (1) an overview of the literature on the timing of exit and work exit routes, (2) descriptive analyses for European countries using Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) data, and (3) descriptive analyses for Norway using the Norwegian Quality-of-life Survey, since Norway is not included in SHARE. Finally, the findings will be discussed.

Part 1. Risk factors for timing of exit and work exit routes. Context and theoretical background

Introduction

Population ageing and the subsequent rising pressures on pension and health systems led to increasing retirement ages in European countries, especially during the past two decades. A series of reforms have been put into practice in many European countries. Increases in retirement ages were implemented along with a rolling back of early retirement schemes and reductions in disability benefits, delaying thus the exit of older workers from the labour market. Furthermore, across Europe, measures were implemented to promote employability, job mobility and demand for older workers, and incentives were provided for older people to stay longer in the labour market.

In 2022, the range in normal retirement ages¹ among the European countries varied between 62 years (in Slovenia, Luxembourg and Greece) and 67 years (in Norway, Denmark and Iceland) for men and between 60 years (in Poland) and 67 years (in Norway, Denmark and Iceland) for women. It is expected that in countries like Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Estonia and Italy the normal retirement age to increase to 70 for men and women who start their career in present days, provided that life expectancy will raise according to projections and links with life expectancy implemented (OECD, 2023).

These current trends in prolonging working lives are substantiated by increasing longevity and the fact that the average effective age of labour market exit is still lower than the normal retirement age in most European countries. Across EU countries, the average life expectancy increased steadily by more than 15 years between 1960 and 2021 in the EU, from 63.2 years in 1960 to 78.6 in 2021 for males, and from 68.3 years to 84.2 for females (European Commission 2023). Effective retirement ages remain lower than the normal retirement ages for the majority of European countries, with some states showing large gaps between the two, like Austria (3.4 for men and 0.9 years for women), Belgium (3.9 and 3.7 years for men and women, respectively) and France (4 for men and 2.5 years for women) (OECD, 2023).

The implemented pension reforms conducted to significant progress in extending the time in the labour market for older people. The employment rate of 55–64-year-old in EU27 nearly

¹ The normal retirement age is defined as the age at which individuals are eligible for retirement benefits from all pension components without penalties, assuming a full career from age 22 (OECD, 2023: 42).

doubled, from 38.1% in 2004 to 63.9% in 2024, with some countries reaching rates as high as 75% (Netherlands) and 78% (Sweden). Still, it is considered that more needs to be done.

Despite developing policies focused on lengthening working lives and their subsequent progress, it becomes apparent that they cannot equally reach all population groups (e.g. low income or people with a poor health status). Substantial socio-economic inequalities that persist in numerous societies represent a challenge in achieving longer working lives.

Many European countries are trying to close the gap in retirement age between men and women. However, women have a more vulnerable situation on the labour market than men, which might still determine them to retire early. Low-income, low-skilled older workers also face important challenges in working longer. Although driven by financial need to remain active in the labour market in their later life, they are also employed in more precarious jobs, have higher risks of poor health and suffer from work strain (Murtin et al., 2022). They also have a shorter life expectancy at 65 of up to five years in comparison to higher skilled (Mosquera et al., 2019), translating into less time spent in retirement. Even when they retire, they might be forced to take up jobs to supplement inadequate pensions. Similar challenges arise for other vulnerable groups like older workers with poor health, those with disabilities, or those with an immigrant status.

Given the increasingly fragmented and precarious nature of employment, it is highly likely that precarious employment trajectories translate into precarious retirements for many groups. Older age itself posits unique issues in terms of poor health, lower levels of physical and social activities, and negative life events like becoming a widower. Moreover, for vulnerable groups, disadvantages tend to accumulate over the life course, making a disproportionate impact in older age on their quality of life. Under these circumstances, vulnerable older workers run the risk of being trapped in an area of precarity marked by declining incomes and limited opportunities to access suitable jobs (Phillipson, 2020).

Against this background we set out to understand the role of individual factors like gender, health limitations, income poverty and care responsibilities in timing of exit and work exit routes in European countries.

Timing of exit and work exit routes. Definitions and typologies

The timing of exit refers to the moment when employed people decide to withdraw from labour market. The timing of work exit, as defined in the literature, refers to the age or relative point at which workers leave their position or career path (Fisher et al., 2016). In empirical terms, retirement timing is used as the gap between normal and effective retirement age (Jurek, 2023). The moment people leave the labour market can be influenced by various factors, including age, health status, financial situation, and labour market conditions. In the context of labour economics, the timing of exit from the labour market is often studied in relation to retirement decisions, job mobility, and labour force participation rates.

In the lightest form, we can quantify timing of exit as an intention, while in the hardest form it can be the actual time of exit which can be the mandatory or recommended age of retirement. Previous research showed that intention to retire might be a better proxy than decisions for retirement behaviour, especially when the issue is planning for policies, because more workers can state a preferred age of retiring than a decision about when to retire (Solem et al., 2016).

However, the match between intention to retire at a preferred age and the possibility to do so in up to five years depends on the opportunity structure (Solem et al., 2016), mostly consisting of national regulations and incentives, organisational-level practices and policies, and cultural norms around ageing and retirement. The likelihood of changes in the opportunity structure and expectations rises with longer time lags between expectations, intentions, and actions. This leads to fewer accurate predictions. Nevertheless, intention to retire is a snapshot of current conditions, related or not to work.

Individuals' stated intention to retire is a reliable indicator of when they are likely to leave the workforce, and predictions regarding retirement intentions can be used to estimate the actual timing of employees' leaving from their jobs, provided that we take into account the fact that these predictions are based on the conditions that are affecting employees now (rather than in the future), such as demographic trends, workplace policies, economic factors, personal circumstances, and labour laws. Therefore, prediction of intention to retire is the actual estimate of time of exit under current circumstances.

Work exit routes refer to the route employed by people when leaving the labour market. Literature shows a diversity of routes based on national and local market regulations. A typology of work exit routes for older workers includes various ways in which older individuals transition out of the labour force. These exit routes can be influenced by factors such as health, social policies, and economic conditions. Common exit routes for older workers may involve early retirement buy-outs, early old-age pensions (Reeuwijk et al., 2017), special age-related schemes, and discriminatory practices leading to job loss. Additionally, the availability of social safety nets, labour market institutions, and educational factors can impact the exit routes for older workers. Typologies use mostly criteria focused on access to pensions or to other routes of exit. The most common non-competing routes to retirement (Brugiavini & Peracchi, 2014) are: (a) old-age pension, (b) early retirement, and (c) disability pension. However, other further classifications (Furunes et al., 2012) centre around distinct pension routes: retirement or exit on disability pension, retirement or exit on optional age pension, ordinary old age pension. At the same time, there are competing exit routes that individuals can choose from: 1. disability benefit, 2. unemployment, 3. early retirement, 4. becoming economically inactive (Reeuwijk et al., 2017).

It is useful to distinguish between push and pull variables when assessing labour market dynamics processes. This distinction can make it clearer how people join or leave the workforce depending on a range of factors, including circumstances and incentives. Push factors, which are frequently unfavourable situations like high unemployment, low living standards, or a lack of possibilities, are what motivate people to leave their current environment. For example, people may look for job abroad due to unstable economies or low pay. In contrast, pull factors represent appealing characteristics that draw people to a new place or opportunity. These might be improved living conditions, better employment conditions, or more pay. For example, workers may relocate from places with fewer employment possibilities to areas with a robust job market.

For the abovementioned routes, push and pull factors can differently interact and play out in distinct welfare regimes and in different countries. The differences in exit routes from labour markets across European welfare state regimes highlight the varying degrees of support provided to workers transitioning out of employment. Countries with comprehensive social safety nets tend to offer more structured and supportive exit pathways compared to those with limited welfare provisions (Reeuwijk et al., 2017). Countries with social democratic regimes (like Scandinavia) usually have strong social security benefits and pension systems. Pull factors such as financial incentives for early retirement are more prominent in this situation, facilitating easier retirement transitions without the drawbacks of involuntary exits brought on by

economic or health constraints (Halleröd et al., 2013). In conservative/Bismarckian welfare systems (like Germany), a combination of push and pull dynamics are at work. Strong pension systems can serve as pull forces, but inflexible labour markets might result in involuntary because of shifting economic conditions, health problems, or more stringent early retirement eligibility requirements. People may be forced out of employment because of economic constraints, but if they do not fit certain requirements, they may not receive much assistance from the pension systems (Ebbinghaus, 2000). Early leave rates are frequently higher in Southern European regimes due to a mix of economic volatility and generous early retirement alternatives. People who are experiencing financial difficulties or health problems can more easily move into retirement or disability benefits when there are several exit routes available (Ebbinghaus & Hofäcker, 2013; Struffolino & Zaccaria, 2020). Liberal regimes generally lack strong pull factors due to limited social benefits. Consequently, older workers may remain in the labour force longer unless faced with significant push factors like job loss or health problems (Ebbinghaus, 2000)

Many European countries offer structured routes for early retirement, often linked to years of service or specific professions. For instance, in Sweden, options include early retirement for individuals with long work histories or those in physically demanding jobs. However, recent reforms have tightened eligibility criteria, making it harder for workers to exit without financial penalties (Bengtsson et al., 2022). Research shows that routes of exit vary significantly between countries based on various contextual factors like national policies, economic conditions, and social safety nets. Countries with Scandinavian welfare state regimes had the lowest absolute risks of early retirement and economic inactivity. The welfare state regimes in Southern Europe have the lowest absolute risks for unemployment and disability benefits.

Countries with robust unemployment benefits, such as Germany and Denmark, provide significant support for those exiting the labour market involuntarily. These benefits often include extended support for older workers who face unemployment, allowing them to transition more smoothly into retirement or other forms of employment (Bengtsson et al., 2022). Conversely, in countries like Greece, the unemployment benefit system is less comprehensive, which can push older workers into early retirement without adequate financial support (Scarpetta & di Noia, 2023). Some Eastern European countries may not have developed systems for recognizing health-related exits, leading to higher rates of informal labour market exits, combined with a prevalence for routes on disability and early retirement.

Individual risk factors for timing of exit and work exit routes

Age, gender, educational attainment, and family status are sociodemographic characteristics that have a significant impact on retirement decisions. Retirement decisions are heavily influenced by age, with older persons frequently evaluating their work prospects, financial preparedness, and health in view of their retirement. Many people may put off retiring due to high levels of involvement in their work or significant chances for personal development (König et al., 2016). Their choices are also greatly influenced by variables including wealth, health, and educational attainment (Beehr & Bennett, 2015). These trends are further complicated by societal norms regarding appropriate retirement ages which affects the likelihood of retirement (Ebbinghaus & Radl, 2015; Hofäcker et al., 2016; Hyde & Dingemans, 2017).

Factors influencing intention to retire can be negative (push factors), driving people out of the labour market, or positive (pull factors), pulling individuals towards exiting at a specific timing. Amongst push factors for intention to retire are health problems (Laires et al., 2020), high job demands and work-related stress (Toczek et al., 2022), low job satisfaction (Oakman & Wells, 2013) as well as various labour markets constraints (Woźniak et al., 2022). Pull factors, those factors that attract individuals towards retirement, can be the desire to spend time with family (De Preter et al., 2013), having a partner who is retired (Kuhn et al., 2021) or financial incentives, like high taxes on continued work or generous early exit schemes. Intentions to retire depend on cultural expectations around retirement age and on opportunity structure available to individuals in their context (Solem et al., 2016). Having a history of interrupted employment across the working life course is associated with a higher intention to exit early (Hofäcker, 2015), while those with a history of unemployment or belonging to lower social classes are more likely to retire earlier, often due to health issues or limited access to continued employment opportunities (Radl, 2013; Ebbinghaus & Radl, 2015).

Gender

Retirement decisions are heavily influenced by gender, with men and women having different opportunities and obstacles when leaving the labour market. Women are more likely than men to take on caregiving roles, which can lead to earlier exits from the labour market, especially when combined with social class background (Radl, 2013). This caregiving burden is compounded by traditional gender norms that assign women primary responsibility for household tasks, further influencing their decisions regarding labour market participation. Women retire earlier across Europe, studies showing that men generally expect to work longer than women. However, women may choose to extend their working lives under specific circumstances, such as financial necessity or family dynamics (Kim et al., 2019). The financial preparedness for retirement also varies by gender; women often have lower retirement savings due to wage disparities and career interruptions for caregiving, which can affect their timing of exit from the labour market. Discontinuous work trajectories brought on by caregiving and family obligations frequently hamper women's retirement planning (Platts et al., 2019; Ebbinghaus & Radl, 2015; Hofäcker et al., 2015) with mixed results, either delaying retirement (König et al., 2016; Raghuraman et al., 2023) or contributing to early exit from the labour market (Carr et al., 2018). Because women work in certain occupations that are dominated by women (these jobs tend to be lower-paying compared to male-dominated fields like engineering or finance) and because their wealth, education, and marital status have a greater impact on their commitment to the labour market (Riekhoff & Järnefelt, 2017), their retirement experiences and timing tend to differ (Riekhoff & Järnefelt, 2017). This disparity can be seen in the fact that women may already be at a financial disadvantage regarding pension benefits as they get closer to retirement because of gender pay inequalities, which in turn, affects retirement timing (Radl, 2013). However, research indicates that other contextual elements are important. Wage discrimination was less common in countries with high levels of women's empowerment in society, centralized collective bargaining, family-friendly legislation, and robust trade union densities (Triventi, 2013).

Health limitations

Health limitations have been proven to be a major factor in exiting labour market (García-Gómez et al., 2010; Rohrbacher & Hasselhorn, 2022). Having various health constraints do not necessarily imply lack of good health. People can have several functional limitations and still be in good health. Adapting to quickly shifting circumstances that jeopardize one's physical, emotional, social, and existential well-being is necessary for maintaining good health (Krahn et

al., 2021). Poor health is a major factor driving early retirement (Hagan et al., 2009; Hess et al., 2021), more precisely poor health stemming from chronic conditions (Bound et al., 1999; Fisher et al., 2016) which impose significant physical and mental burdens on individuals (Fisher et al., 2016). Health limitations affect intention to retire (Laires et al., 2020) and we know that individuals with poor health status are more likely to have higher retirement rates (Brugiavini & Perrachi, 2014) and that workers with poor health are more likely to leave the labour force earlier than workers with good health (Reeuwijk et al., 2017). Studies on mental health show that individuals beyond the age of 50 with depressive symptoms are at increased risk of losing paid employment (Porru et al., 2019). An early exit may be impacted by age-related health issues or a notable decline in pertinent abilities at the individual level (Steiber & Kohli, 2017). Even so, the role of health status and limitations can be distinct when support for early retirement plans and socially prescribed standards that specify a normal retirement age are in place. Furthermore, due to decreased retirement benefits, older workers may continue to work past the official statutory retirement age. This could happen in labour markets that are subtly affected by economic recessions and therefore with consistent disruptions in labour market participation. Good health, the necessity of preserving one's identity and function (role continuation), and a rise in total income (Markova & Tosheva, 2020) can be important factors that influence a later exit.

Therefore, certain exit routes may be differently linked to health influences (Richardson et al., 2019). Workers with poor health have different risks to exit through particular routes (Reeuwijk et al., 2017). Poor health, functional limitations, and mental health issues like depression are strongly linked to a higher risk of exiting the workforce via disability benefits (De Breij et al., 2020). While early retirement is another exit route, its association with poor health is less pronounced than that of disability benefits (Hasselhorn et al., 2022). Nevertheless, individuals with poorer health are still more likely to retire early (Hasselhorn et al., 2022; Runge et al., 2024). However, these impacts of health on exit routes are shaped by welfare state provisions (Richardson et al., 2019). In countries with generous welfare states, persons with health restrictions retire sooner and more often via disability pensions, whereas in countries with inadequate welfare state provisions, they are forced to retire later. For example, risks of early retirement and becoming economically inactive were discovered to be lowest in Scandinavian welfare state regimes. For disability benefit and unemployment, risks were lowest in Southern European welfare state regimes (Reeuwijk et al., 2017).

Care responsibilities

To understand how formal and informal care are articulated in EU countries, many care regime typologies were created (Leitner, 2003, 2014; Saraceno 2016). Based on the degree to which various welfare states offer care services (in kind), and the weight placed on the family as a welfare producer, these discussions mostly centred on the conflict between familialization and de-familialization (Ungerson, 2005; Le Bihan et al., 2019). Familialistic policies mandate the reliance of individuals in need of care on their family members in addition to requiring (and simultaneously enabling) the family to provide for their members' care requirements (Leitner, 2003). From a labour market perspective, there is a conflict between the labour force required and encouraged by national policies that want to prolong working life past retirement and the voluntary care giving pool supplied by those who retire early to care for their family members. Since women tend to be those who provide care, future concerns address a possible gender pay gap between those who continue to work and those who retire early to provide care work (Carlstedt et al., 2018).

Care responsibilities, especially informal ones within families, are commonly in conflict with paid work for women (Platts et al., 2019), but less for men (Schneider et al., 2013; Schmitz et al., 2023). Younger older women, as well as immigrant women are consistently part of the eldercare labour force (Szeman, 2012), however informal labour affects this sector and can hinder an adequate analysis of push and pull factors in retainment of younger older women. Women's late employment is either shaped by unpaid care or paid (full- or part-time) work but not both, whereas men's late working life is mainly shaped by full-time work (Schmitz, 2023). Family history in earlier life is linked to unpaid care and part-time work—an association strongest in liberal and southern welfare regimes (Schmitz, 2023). When both men and women exit the labour market because of care responsibilities, women tend to do so because caregiving is time-consuming, while men tend to do so if caregiving is a physical burden (Schneider et al., 2013).

Income poverty

Income poverty plays a critical role in shaping retirement experiences and outcomes. As economic conditions fluctuate and social security systems evolve, addressing the needs of those at risk of pre-retirement poverty is essential for ensuring that all individuals can retire with dignity and financial security. Systemic reforms targeting income support and employment opportunities for older adults are necessary to mitigate these challenges and improve retirement outcomes for low-income populations. Literature shows that the relationship between income poverty and retirement timing is a critical area of research, particularly as populations age and the dynamics of work and retirement evolve (Fisher et al., 2016).

Individuals with low income or those who have experienced poverty during their working lives often face significant challenges when approaching retirement. A study highlighted that those in low-paid jobs are likely to continue working until reaching the statutory retirement age due to financial necessity, despite a desire to retire (Swain et al., 2020). This reflects a broader trend where economic constraints dictate retirement timing, pushing many to delay their exit from the workforce. The interplay between health and income poverty is crucial in determining retirement timing. Research indicates that poor health has a stronger association with early retirement compared to low income alone (Rad et al., 2017). This suggests that while financial resources are vital, health status can significantly influence the decision to retire early or continue working, being, as discussed earlier, the major factor affecting timing. A life course approach reveals that experiences of poverty throughout an individual's life contribute to their perceptions and decisions regarding retirement. For example, individuals who have consistently faced low pay may develop a heightened awareness of their financial insecurity as they approach retirement age, influencing their timing and readiness to retire (Swain et al., 2020). The transition into retirement can be abrupt, especially following significant life events such as widowhood. Research shows that the death of a spouse can lead to an immediate risk of falling into poverty for the surviving partner (Holden et al., 1988; Biro, 2013; Zaidi, 2014), often linked more closely to the event of retirement than to gradual income erosion over time (Holden et al., 1988). This highlights the vulnerability of older adults in managing their financial stability post-retirement. Moreover, if death of a spouse coincides with the pre-retirement stages, it can affect the timing of exit. However, these life course events' effects seem to be different in different countries. Cross-national variations in coverage, particularly the generosity of survivor benefits, may contribute to some country-specific variance in the effects of widowhood on the financial well-being of surviving spouses. In countries with more generous survivor benefits, the drop in the economic well-being of widowed households is less pronounced (Van Winkle et al., 2024), proving the importance of various social policies circumscribed to different welfare systems.

The increasing normal retirement ages in many countries exacerbate the challenges faced by low-income workers. As these workers are often compelled to remain employed longer than they wish, it raises concerns about their health and well-being during this extended working period (Swain et al., 2020).

High income is associated with voluntary retirement, allowing individuals to choose their retirement timing based on preference rather than necessity (Radl, 2013; Scharn et al., 2018). For late retirement, financial stability and economic necessity are important motivators, particularly for professionals who frequently continue to work after retirement to save money or maintain a professional lifestyle (Silver et al., 2016). Many older persons are forced to delay retirement due to inadequate retirement savings (Galkutė & Herrera, 2020). Longer working lives are encouraged by financial incentives including bonuses, increased pay, and flexible pension plans (Galkutė & Herrera, 2020). Economic circumstances are also very important. Regardless of their individual retirement goals, older persons may need to continue working during recessions or in high-cost areas. Those with lower incomes and no significant savings are more affected by this pressure (Damman, 2016; König et al., 2016; Pettersson, 2014; Madero-Cabib & Kaeser, 2016).

Working conditions

While individual factors tell a particular story about who are those in a position of vulnerability, working conditions matter significantly in retirement intentions (Münderlein et al., 2013), mostly because, unlike the actual retirement turnover, which is dependent of contextual exit regulations in place at a particular moment in time, intentions form in workplace settings and have been proven to be connected with motivators available in workplace environments (Münderlein et al., 2013). Job satisfaction plays a significant role in retirement intentions (Zacher & Rudolph, 2017). Instead of prolonging their working lives, employees who are unhappy at their jobs are more likely to retire early (Prakash et al., 2019). Conflicts and unfavourable work conditions can discourage late exit, particularly when it comes to co-workers' support of EWL (Reeuwijk et al., 2013). Low quality of work measured as effort-reward imbalance and low control is associated with intended early retirement (Siegrist et al., 2007). The imbalance between effort and reward in the workplace proved to be a factor in intention to retire early (Toczek et al., 2022; Sousa-Ribeiro et al., 2024), for many types of employment biographies (Toczek et al., 2022) while recognition of work is also associated with late retirement (Edge et al., 2017; Chen & Gardiner, 2019). The effort-reward imbalance (ERI) model focuses on a mismatch between high efforts put forth and low incentives obtained at work (Siegrist, 1996). It is a theoretical model of a psychosocial work environment that has negative impacts on health and well-being. Research shows that people are more likely to report retirement intentions and to have unfavourable working conditions if their social status is lower (Wahrendorf et al., 2013). A negative psychosocial work environment can account for some of the correlation between retirement intentions and occupational position (Wahrendorf et al., 2013). Therefore, the effects of an effort-reward imbalance in the workplace might be greater for workers with low occupational position.

Summary

The current literature review focused on individual factors related to gender, care responsibilities, health and income poverty that affect timing of exit from the labour market and work exit routes.

Timing of exit refers to the moment when employed people decide to withdraw from the labour market. This is often influenced by factors such as age, gender, health, market conditions, welfare regimes and financial status as well as structural and cultural norms. The literature highlights various exit routes, with different exit routes that individuals can encounter in different labour market settings, ranging from unemployment and disability benefits to standard pensions and early retirement. Structured pathways for labour force exit exist across Europe with better unemployment benefits and incentives smoothing the transition into retirement for older workers who face unemployment.

Retirement decisions can be driven by push factors, such as health issues, job demands, or dissatisfaction, and pull factors, like the desire to spend more time with family or financial incentives for retiring (positive – early exit schemes or negative – taxes on continued employment). Cultural expectations and individual work histories also impact communication about retiring early.

Much of literature focuses on the importance of gender in retirement decisions. Women are often primary caregivers, leading to earlier exits from the job market. Women also typically have less retirement savings because of wage gaps and interruptions in their careers, resulting in diverse retirement experiences compared to men. The wage gap and its impact on retirement is often less prevalent in more egalitarian societies. However, different welfare systems provide varying levels of support for easing caregiving responsibilities, influenced by the degree of de-familialisation policies.

Health concerns and limitations are significant factors influencing early exit. Poor health, especially chronic issues, pushes people toward early retirement, especially in countries with strong welfare provisions. Mental health problems, such as depression, can increase the risk of job loss for those over 50. Age-related skill decline can also be a factor leading to early exit. Health impacts exit through various pathways, with poor health being strongly associated with a higher likelihood of leaving the workforce for disability benefits. Welfare states play a crucial role in shaping these exit routes.

Income poverty significantly influences retirement timing, often in conjunction with other factors such as health and limited access to (new) job opportunities. Poverty experienced during one's working life profoundly shapes retirement experiences, with economic constraints forcing low-income workers into prolonged employment, while poor health compels them to exit the workforce. Life course events, such as the death of a spouse, can abruptly and significantly impact financial stability, varying by country. High income allows for voluntary retirement and labour force exit delays for financial or “prestige” purposes. Low income or inadequate savings can lead to longer employment or labour force re-entry, especially during recessions or in high-cost areas. Job satisfaction plays a significant role in retirement intentions, with dissatisfied employees tending to retire earlier, as do those experiencing an imbalance between effort and reward or those with low social status.

Part 2. The role of individual risk factors in exit from the labour market in Europe

In this section, we set out to understand the role of individual factors like gender, health limitations, care responsibilities, and income poverty in the timing of exit from the labour market by using data from European countries included in the Study of Ageing, Retirement and Health in Europe (SHARE).

First, we examine retirement intentions, as this indicator captures personal preferences for retirement. As a depiction of the current circumstances of older workers, the intention to retire allows us to best describe the role of individual factors in exiting the labour market. We employ bivariate analysis to describe the relationship between various social characteristics, such as gender, health limitations, care responsibilities, and income poverty, and intentions to retire. Furthermore, we use regression models to understand how the relationships between these individual characteristics and the intention to retire early change under the moderating influence of other factors (e.g., whether the effect of gender is diminished for individuals with health limitations). Second, we describe the timing of exit from the labour market. Third, we focus on exit routes from the labour market.

Data and sample

Study of Ageing, Retirement and Health in Europe (SHARE) is a longitudinal survey. The target population consists of all persons with the age of 50 years or more who live regularly in their country, are not incarcerated, hospitalised or out of the country during the survey. Spouses/partners are also included in the target population even if they are younger than 50 years. SHARE includes people living in nursing or residential homes if they are covered in the sampling frame from which the baseline/refreshments samples are drawn (Bergmann, Wagner, and Börsch-Supan, 2021).

We use data from wave 9 carried out between October 2021 and September 2022 by means of Computer-Assisted Personal Interview (CAPI) (SHARE, 2024). This wave covers the population with the age 50 years or older from the following European countries: Austria, Germany, Sweden, Netherlands, Spain, Italy, France, Denmark, Greece, Switzerland, Belgium, Czech Republic, Poland, Luxembourg, Hungary, Portugal, Slovenia, Estonia, Croatia, Lithuania, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Finland, Latvia, Malta, Romania, Slovakia. The total pooled sample consists of 68.192 people (see Annex 1. Country sample sizes). Of the total sample, 14.424 people are still employed, all others being inactive. Out of those not active on labour market, 44.580 people are retired. Different subsamples are included in our analysis. In order to understand intentions to retire early we include older workers still active on the labour market (N=14.424). When studying the time of exit and work exit routes, we include persons retired in the past 15 years, between 2006 and 2022, (N=10.999), avoiding thus too much heterogeneity among the retired population due to changes in legislation. We analyse the pooled samples due to the small number of cases for each country and, only where possible, we report country-specific values.

Unweighted data is used since our aim is to understand associations between variables (e.g. gender and the intention to retire early) rather than to give population-level estimates, and since we select specific categories such as those retired in the last 15 years, which are not easily accounted for by the weighting system.

In regression models for intention to retire early we include random effects for country level to account for the country level variation even if we do not control for country level variables. In other words, we consider that people work and live in countries with specific labour markets and pension policies. Therefore, we acknowledge that intention to retire early may vary across countries not just due to individual level factors but also due to country level factors.

Variables

Outcomes

First, we aim to understand the intention of early retirement of older workers. We use answers to the question: *Thinking about your present job, would you like to retire as early as you can from this job? Yes or No.* We use this as a binary variable *yes* having the value 1, otherwise 0.

Second, we concentrate on the actual time of exit measured with the age at retirement computed as the difference between the year of retirement and the year of birth. We use this as a continuous variable.

Finally, we focus on work exit routes. Respondents were asked to choose all the main reasons why they retired from this list (i.e. multiple choice question): *became eligible for public pension; became eligible for private occupational pension; became eligible for a private pension; was offered an early retirement option/window with special incentives or bonus; made redundant (for example pre-retirement); own ill health; ill health of relative or friend; to retire at same time as spouse or partner; to spend more time with family; to enjoy life.* Therefore, we have ten binary variables in the dataset, selected motives having the value 1, otherwise 0.

Covariates: individual risk factors

For gender we have two values, male and female².

For health limitations we use the global activity limitation index or GALI (Gruber, Wagner, and Batta 2024; Van Oyen et al. 2006) which is a single-item direct measure: *For the past 6 months at least, to what extent have you been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? with three levels Severely limited; Limited, but not severely; Not limited.* We combine the first two categories into a single category *limited* contrasting it with the category *Not limited*.

For material situation we use subjective income which is a single-item direct measure: *Thinking of your household's total monthly income, would you say that your household is able to make ends meet? with four levels; With great difficulty; With some difficulty; Fairly easily; Easily.* We combine the first two categories into a single category *With difficulty* and the last two categories into a single category *Easily*.

² We analyse data using R. R uses factors, which is a convenient way to work with categorical variables because we do not need to create separate dummy variables. Instead, R creates virtual dummy variables. We are using this approach with our categorical variables if not otherwise specified.

For care burden we use the subjective indicator: *How often do you think that family responsibilities prevent you from doing what you want to do? with four levels Often; Sometimes; Rarely; Never.* We combine the first two categories into a single category *Often* or *Sometimes* and the last two categories into a single category *Rarely* or *Never*.

Control variables

Working conditions might influence the intention to retire early and, although they are not the main focus of our study, we control for them. We use a version of the Effort-Reward Imbalance (ERI) scale that is available in SHARE (Gruber, Wagner, & Batta, 2024) based on the theoretical model with the same name (Siegrist et al., 2004). This scale, with acceptable psychometric properties (Siegrist, Li, & Montano, 2014), has items measuring the effort at work and the rewards received for their effort. The effort items are: *My job is physically demanding; I am under constant time pressure due to a heavy workload.* The reward items are: *I receive adequate support in difficult situations; I receive the recognition I deserve for my work; Considering all my efforts and achievements, my salary is/my earnings are adequate; My job promotion prospects/prospects for job advancement/job promotion prospects are poor; My job security is poor.* The response scale is for all items: *strongly agree; agree; disagree; strongly disagree.* We reversed the response scale for the effort items so that higher scores reflect higher effort at work. The response scale for the first three items measuring reward were also reversed so that the sum of all reward items to reflect higher reward from work. Although effort and reward can be analysed separately, we follow the theoretical model which argues that the imbalance between these two dimensions is the most important. Consequently, we compute an index variable as the ratio between effort and reward summative scores. Since effort has two items while reward has five items, authors of the scale use a weighting factor of 0.4, which is the ratio between the number of effort items and the number of reward items, 2/5. The effort-reward imbalance variable is the result of $\text{effort}/(\text{reward} * 0.4)$. The effort-reward ratio will take values between 0.25 and 4. The lower the ratio the more rewarding a job is, given the effort put into it, while a higher ratio indicates an imbalance between effort and reward. We use the effort-reward ratio as a continuous variable. In regression models we use the centred around mean ratio to make the estimation of the intercept more meaningful and reduce multicollinearity.

We include educational attainment as a control variable because education can be strongly correlated with both the intention to retire early and income poverty, while these relationships can also be gendered. In SHARE, information about education is included as ISCED 1997 with six levels: primary education or first stage of basic education (code 1), lower secondary or second stage of basic education (code 2), (upper) secondary education (code 3), post-secondary non-tertiary education (code 4), first stage of tertiary education (code 5), second stage of tertiary education (code 6). Beside these levels, the variable in the dataset includes people with no education, still in school, or in other situation. For our analysis, due to small number of cases for no education and second stage of tertiary education categories, we combined people with no education with primary education and first stage with second stage of tertiary education, while we excluded people still in school or in other situations. We treat this variable as factor in our analysis.

Analytical technique

Intentions to retire early. We start with describing intention for the overall sample and for each country. Then we investigate the bivariate relationship with each focal predictor and control variable. We then move to binary logistic regression models. First, we run a model only with

focal predictors: gender, health limitations, care responsibilities, and income poverty. Furthermore, we add to the model two control variables: working conditions and education. Finally, we add 2-by-2 interaction terms between focal predictors. The template for models with interactions is $\text{outcome} = \text{predictor 1} + \text{predictor 2} + \text{predictor 3} + \text{predictor 4} + \text{control 1} + \text{control 2} + \text{predictor 1} * \text{predictor 2}$. For example, we first run a model with the interaction between gender and health situation, then the model between gender and material situation and so on. As already mentioned, we take into account that people are nested within countries. Consequently, we include random effects for country level in all models. Regression models use cases with valid values for all variables in models, therefore the analysis sample is smaller than the initial sample as outlined in the section "Data and sample".

Since some respondents retired or decided to leave the labour market before being asked about the focal predictors, we do not assess associations between age at retirement, motives for leaving, and the focal predictors or control variables.

Results

Intentions of early retirement

Respondents are classified as people who intent to retire early and who do not want to retire early.

Figure 1 Intention to retire early by country. Percent

Almost half of the older workers, 46%, intend to retire early. This percentage varies by country (Figure 1), from a minimum value of 17% in Estonia to a maximum value of 84% in Lithuania. Lithuania differentiates itself sharply from the other countries in the sample, even from those with similar institutional settings: Latvia and Estonia. The next highest percent of workers with the intention to retire early is 71% in Slovenia. We notice several clusters of countries with similar values such as Latvia, Bulgaria, Denmark, Sweden, Croatia and Belgium revolving between 35% and 37%. The PATHS2INCLUDE countries included in SHARE is Germany, Italy, Spain, Romania, Luxembourg, and Poland. These countries are quite different, with Spain having the largest share of older workers with the intention to retire early (70%), followed by Italy (63%), Romania (63%), Poland (52%), and with Germany having the lowest share (48%). A recent research note from Eurostat³ shows that the majority of older workers retire when reaching the standard age for retirement (i.e. old-age pension). Interestingly, the Baltic countries - Estonia (55%), Latvia (44%), and Lithuania (44%), have the highest share of older workers who continued working after reaching the standard retirement age. This is in line with our findings that Estonia and Latvia have some of the lowest shares of older workers intending to retire early, which contrasts with our findings about Lithuania. According to Eurostat data⁴, Lithuanians, in comparisons with Latvians and Estonians, are less likely to report staying in the labour market for financial necessity and for staying socially integrated, but more likely to report staying due to financial incentives and because they enjoy working and being productive.

Figure 2 Intention to retire early by gender, health limitations, income poverty, and care responsibilities (all countries)

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20241209-1>

⁴ Source of data: Eurostat lfs0_23pens08, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfs0_23pens06/default/table?lang=en

Figure 2 shows that the percentages of males and females who intend to retire early are similar. However, the percentage of those who intend to retire early is higher for individuals who are limited in their activities due to health problems (53%) in comparison with those not limited (43%), making ends meet with difficulty (53%) in comparison with those making ends meet easily (42%), and have family responsibilities that often or sometimes prevent them from doing what they want to do (51%) versus those not having this problem (44%).

Figure 3 Effort-Reward Ratio distribution for intention to retire early or not (all countries)

Working conditions may also influence the intention to retire early. Figure 3 shows that the median ERR is slightly higher for those who intend to retire early (median = 1) than for those who do not (median = 0.8). Since higher values of ERR reflect more effort and less reward from the workplace, this difference suggests that work stress might be a reason for early retirement. Using the ERR index we cannot assess which type of rewards is more important, extrinsic (i.e. salary, promotion prospects, job security) or intrinsic (i.e. recognition), but it is likely that physical and mental workload contribute more to the intention to retire early.

The percentage of older workers who intend to retire early decreases with education level as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Intention to retire early by education level

Multivariate analysis allows us to take into account individual risk factors simultaneously. First, we focus on focal predictors which are gender, health limitations, care responsibilities, and income poverty and then we control for working conditions and education. For each model we take into account that people are nested in countries. Results for these models are in Table 1, while we use figures to represent regression coefficients as odds ratios.

Variable	Model with focal predictors		Model with focal predictors and control variables		Model with focal predictors, control variables, and interaction term	
	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value	Estimate	P-value
Intercept	0.51	0.00	-0.07	0.77	-0.22	0.38
Gender: female	0.09	0.04	0.17	0.01	0.41	0.00
Health limitations: no	-0.51	0.00	-0.33	0.00	-0.33	0.00
Make ends meet: easily	-0.33	0.00	-0.17	0.04	-0.17	0.03
Care responsibilities: no	-0.20	0.00	-0.11	0.12	0.10	0.37
Working conditions (higher values more effort than reward)			1.55	0.00	1.55	0.00
ISCED-97 code 2			0.18	0.36	0.18	0.38
ISCED-97 code 3			0.26	0.16	0.25	0.17

ISCED-97 code 4			0.16	0.46	0.16	0.47
ISCED-97 code 5 or ISCED-97 code 6			0.10	0.58	0.10	0.59
Gender: female * Care responsibilities: no					-0.33	0.02
Number of cases:	9520		5407		5391	
Number of countries:	27		27		27	

Note. The dependent variable is intention to retire early (value 1 for yes, and value 0 for no). Reference categories are male, with health limitations, making ends meet with difficulty, having care responsibilities, no education or ISCED-97 code 1 (primary education).

Table 1 Binary logistic regression models for intention to retire early

Figure 5 Individual risk factors for intention to retire early

As shown in Figure 5 the odds of intending to retire early are lower for those living in households able to make ends meet easily, are not limited in daily life due to health problems, and do not have family responsibilities that prevent them from doing what they want to do. Women have slightly higher odds of intending to retire early compared to men. Although we did not use the country-level risk factors in the model, we took into account that people are nested in countries. Therefore, we see that when accounting for both individual-level factors and differences between countries, the model explains 16% of the variance in the intention to retire early. The individual-level factors alone explain 2% of the variance. This suggests that these predictors have

a relatively small effect on the outcome and that country-level differences play a significant role in influencing retirement intentions, emphasising the importance of contextual factors such as policies, culture, or economic conditions. For example, not intending to retire early when you are able to make ends meet easily could be explained by having financial disincentives/penalties for early retirement.

Figure 6 Individual risk factors for intention to retire early

By adding the effort-reward ratio and education into the model, Figure 6 shows that the odds of intending to retire early are higher for those with a higher effort-reward ratio. When the effort is higher than rewards, the chance of intending to retire early increases. Care responsibilities are not statistically significant in this model. The regression coefficient for gender is larger, which may suggest that one of these control variables acts like a suppressor variable, increasing the predictive power of gender by partialling out irrelevant variance that was obscuring the effect. The regression coefficients for the other predictors are smaller which may suggest that one of these control variables acts like a confounder variable, being associated with both the outcome and predictors. The individual-level factors alone explain 11% of the variance. The increase in the marginal R2 (from 2% to 11%) suggests that most likely the effort-reward ratio is an important predictor of the intention to retire early. The conditional R2 increased from 16% to 24% showing that country-level differences still play an important role. The results suggest that the balance between effort and reward is a key driver of retirement intentions, in addition to the effects of country-level variation.

Since the intersection between individual risk factors, is key to our analysis, we tested all 2-by-2 interaction terms between focal predictors (i.e. gender*health limitations, gender*income poverty, gender*care responsibilities, health limitations*income poverty, health limitations*care responsibilities, income poverty*care responsibilities). Only the interaction between gender and care responsibilities was statistically significant for 95% level of confidence while controlling for the other focal individual risk factors and control variables. Therefore, the relationship between care responsibilities and the intention to retire early has a higher probability to vary by gender. In contrast, the other models testing interactions between various pairs of predictors did not reveal statistically significant interaction effects, suggesting that these relationships are not meaningfully moderated by the interacting variables in this dataset. This result indicates that the relationship between our focal predictors and early retirement intentions is similar for different moderators. For example, while women who are not limited by health problems may have slightly higher predicted probabilities of early retirement compared to men, the effect is not statistically robust. So, while there is a slight difference between men and women, it is not consistent enough to confidently say that women are definitely more likely to retire earlier than men in this situation.

The model with the statistically significant interaction between gender and care burden assesses whether the effect of caring responsibilities is different for men and women (see Table 1 and Figure 7).

Women are 50% (OR=1.50) more likely to have early retirement intentions than men when they have care responsibilities, holding all other variables constant. Healthy people are 28% (OR=0.72) less likely of intending to retire early than those who are limited due to health problems. Older workers living in households able to make ends meet easily are 16% (OR=0.84) less likely to intend early retirement. Good health and secure financial situation emerge as important factors for not considering early retirement. The effort-reward ratio is statistically significant in this model too, a one-unit increase in the effort-reward ratio being associated with four times the chance (OR=4.70) of early retirement intentions. The negative coefficient for the interaction term shows that not having care responsibilities is less important among women than men regarding intention to retire early. This suggests that even when both genders have similar care responsibilities, women are still more inclined to plan for an early retirement than men. It is possible that care responsibilities are more important in shaping retirement decisions for men in comparison to women as women are more used to care responsibilities and consequently more inclined to assume the role of caretaker even more after retirement.

Figure 7 Interaction between gender and care burden for intention to retire early

Time of exit

In this section we focus on actual time of exit measured as the effective retirement age, which is the difference between year of retirement and year of birth. Since age at retirement is in the past for most respondents in SHARE while our covariates take values for the present, we will employ univariate analysis for describing this variable.

Figure 8 Age at retirement, all countries, 2007-2022

The distribution of age at retirement is shown in Figure 8. The mean age at retirement is 62.2 years and the median age at retirement is 63 years. The standard deviation is 4.3 years, and the range is between 39 and 88 years. The age can be as low as 39 since in this sample we include people who retired for different reasons, not only for reaching the standard retirement age. The same is true for the maximum age of retirement.

The mean age at retirement varies by country (Table 2), with some countries having a higher mean age at retirement than others, for example Denmark or the Netherlands. On the other hand, we have countries with a lower mean age at retirement, for example, Romania and Slovenia. In general, the mean retirement ages are in line with statutory retirement age, although we notice higher discrepancy towards earlier time of exit in Austria, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Bulgaria, or Romania.

Country	Mean retirement age in SHARE 2022	Median retirement age in SHARE 2022	Mean retirement age in SHARE 2022: men / women	Median retirement age in SHARE 2022: men / women	Statutory retirement age (2024): men/women
Austria	60.5	60	60.9 / 60.1	62/ 60	65 / 60 y 6 months
Germany	63.5	64			66
Sweden	65.4	65			63–69; 66*
Netherlands	65.1	66			67
Spain	63.0	64			66 yrs 6 months

Country	Mean retirement age in SHARE 2022	Median retirement age in SHARE 2022	Mean retirement age in SHARE 2022: men / women	Median retirement age in SHARE 2022: men / women	Statutory retirement age (2024): men/women
Italy	63	63			67
France	62	62			62 yrs 6 months
Denmark	64.8	65			67; 67*
Greece	63.7	65			67
Switzerland	64.3	64	64.6 / 64.1	65 / 64	65 / 64
Belgium	63.0	64			65
Czech Republic	61.5	62			64 yrs 2 months
Poland	61.5	61	63.3 / 60.3	63 / 60	65 / 60
Luxembourg	60.8	60			65
Hungary	61.5	62			65
Portugal	62.2	63			66 yrs 4 months
Slovenia	59.7	60			65
Estonia	64.2	64			64 yrs 9 months
Croatia	60.9	61	61.2 / 60.5	62 / 61	65 / 63 yrs 6 months
Lithuania	62.7	63	63.2 / 62.3	64 / 63	64 yrs 8 months / 64 yrs 4 months
Bulgaria	60.8	61			67
Cyprus	63.7	64			65
Finland	63.2	64			64 yrs 6 months–69 yrs; 65*
Latvia	62.5	63			64 yrs 9 months
Malta	61.8	61			64
Romania	59.8	60	60.8 / 58.8	61 / 59	65 / 62
Slovakia	61.1	62			63 yrs 2 months

Table 2 Retirement ages in different countries (*the retirement age of the national pension has been separated from that of the earnings-related pension with a semicolon)⁵

Figure 9 Age at retirement by gender (all countries)

The mean age at retirement for females is 61.9 while for males is 62.6. Figure 9 shows that the peak of the distribution is around 60 years for females and 65 for male, being consistent with standard retirement ages in many countries.

Earlier, we observed that a portion of older workers intend to retire early, with this share being significant in some countries. In this section, we see that the average retirement age tends to align closely with statutory retirement ages. These findings suggest that, at least in some countries, older workers may resist increases to statutory retirement ages.

Work exit routes

In this section, we examine the various routes of work exit. Respondents were asked to choose their reasons for retiring, with the option to select multiple reasons.

⁵ Source: <https://www.etk.fi/en/work-and-pensions-abroad/international-comparisons/retirement-ages/#:~:text=At%20the%20moment%2C%20retirement%20at,retirement%20age%20to%2067%20years.>

For which reasons did you retire?
multiple responses possible

Figure 10 Work exit routes responses

Figure 10 illustrates the distribution of responses for each reason for retirement. The majority of respondents (79%) reported exiting through the public pension route. This was followed by 8% citing their own ill health, 6% indicating early retirement incentives, 5% choosing to enjoy life, and 4% opting for a private occupational pension. The other reasons have much lower frequencies. Although increasing the statutory retirement age is usually seen as the proper measure for keeping people in the labour market, we should also take into account the fact that in some countries more than half of the older workers intend to retire early. Also, our results showed that effort-reward imbalance is a covariate of this intention. So, increasing the age of retirement should take into consideration the national context as well as the significance of individual factors.

Figure 11 Work exit routes unique responses

Figure 10 reports responses given that the question was a multiple-choice one. Switching to unique choices, we see from Figure 11. that public pension is the main exit route for 79% of the respondents. The second most frequent reason is ill health with 8%, followed by early retirement incentives with 6%, enjoying life with 5%, and private occupational pension with 4%. The other reasons are less frequent.

Country	Public pension	Private occupational pension	Private pension	Early retirement incentives	Made redundant	Ill health	Ill health others	Retire with partner	Spend more time with family
Austria	86	1	0	2	1	12	0	0	1
Germany	75	7	2	8	1	13	1	1	4
Sweden	60	35	16	7	3	8	1	5	12
Netherlands	58	23	2	11	7	5	1	2	6
Spain	74	0	0	8	1	13	2	1	9
Italy	89	7	1	2	1	2	0	0	0
France	61	17	24	6	0	6	1	2	5

Country	Public pension	Private occupational pension	Private pension	Early retirement incentives	Made redundant	Ill health	Ill health others	Retire with partner	Spend more time with family
Denmark	26	16	3	23	5	15	2	6	21
Greece	96	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	1
Switzerland	71	7	2	5	3	4	0	2	4
Belgium	83	1	1	6	2	6	1	1	2
Czech Republic	78	0	0	4	4	9	1	0	3
Poland	96	0	0	2	1	2	0	0	0
Luxembourg	90	0	3	2	2	3	1	2	0
Hungary	81	1	0	12	0	5	0	0	0
Portugal	60	5	0	8	4	19	1	0	1
Slovenia	86	0	0	4	0	8	1	0	0
Estonia	79	0	0	5	4	8	1	0	5
Croatia	69	1	0	13	3	11	2	1	2
Lithuania	94	0	1	0	4	6	1	1	5
Bulgaria	87	1	0	0	0	13	0	0	0
Cyprus	77	1	0	4	3	5	1	1	4
Finland	79	1	1	4	1	13	1	1	1
Latvia	88	0	0	5	1	5	0	0	0
Malta	82	0	0	2	3	6	0	0	3
Romania	79	0	0	1	0	18	0	0	0
Slovakia	90	1	0	2	0	8	0	0	0

Table 3 Reasons by country. Percent

Table 3 presents the percentage of respondents from each country exiting the labour market through a specific route. Some countries exhibit high reliance on public pensions, with, for example, Greece and Poland each at 96%, Lithuania at 94%, Slovakia and Luxembourg each at 90%. In contrast, Denmark shows a markedly lower reliance on public pensions (26%), suggesting a greater diversification of retirement income sources. Sweden and the Netherlands demonstrate significant contributions from private occupational pensions, accounting for 35% and 23%, respectively. France also shows a higher rate of private pension usage at 24%, indicating that private savings and occupational schemes play a role in retirement planning in some countries. The prevalence of early retirement incentives varies, with Denmark standing out at 23%, followed by Croatia (13%), Hungary (12%), the Netherlands (11%) and Germany (8%).

This suggests that some countries offer more robust early retirement programs. Conversely, Greece and Poland show negligible reliance on private pensions or early retirement incentives, with a striking 96% of retirees relying solely on public pensions. Romania and Bulgaria seem to have only two pathways out of labour market, public pension and ill health. Enjoy life was a motive for retirement for significant numbers of older workers from Denmark (38%), Sweden (28%), the Netherlands and Switzerland (18%), and France (13%). Of course, this is not an actual path out of the labour market, but it is an important information about the motives behind choosing one or another path. Overall, the table reveals distinct patterns in retirement support systems, with Northern and Western European countries displaying a more balanced mix of public, occupational, and private pensions. The variation in early retirement incentives also underscores differences in policy approaches to workforce exit strategies across Europe.

Figure 12 Public pension by gender within each country

In most countries, women and men show very similar selection rates, with slight variations. However, in a few cases like Switzerland and the Netherlands, the difference between male and female selection is more pronounced, with females typically selecting public pensions at slightly higher rates (Figure 12).

Summary

The intention to retire early among older workers vary across European countries. While 46% of older workers in the pooled sample intend to retire early, there's significant variation in intentions by country, ranging from 17% in Estonia to 84% in Lithuania. Baltic countries (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania) display interesting patterns, with Lithuania emerging as an outlier. Western countries display a mixed picture of intentions, ranging from 24% in Switzerland to 61% in France. Eastern European societies also contrast in terms of peoples' intentions to leave the labour market, from 35% in Bulgaria to 63% in Romania.

When looking at individual factors associated with an early exit from the labour market measured by intentions, results show that gender is not related with early exit, while health limitations, financial strain and care burden are risk factors for an early exit. Older workers who are limited in their activities due to health problems, those who are making ends meet with difficulty and those who have family responsibilities are more likely to express intentions of early exit in comparison to individuals who do not have these types of constraints. Furthermore, higher Effort-Reward Ratio (ERR) is associated with increased intention to retire early.

Multivariate analysis results largely reinforce descriptive results, showing intentions to early retire being lower among those who do not have health limitations, financial strain or care responsibilities. When taking into consideration all these individual constraints, women appear to be more inclined to an early exit. Again, quality of working conditions is a significant circumstance in determining retirement intentions. Nevertheless, individual level factors have limited explanatory power in exit, country level factors probably being mostly responsible for the patterns of intentions.

When looking at the combined effect of individual factors, results show that the interaction between gender and care burden is statistically significant. In similar circumstances of care giving, women show higher retiring intentions than men.

The actual time of exit from the labour market, measured as the effective retirement age, show the expected variation in average retirement age across countries. Countries like Denmark, Netherlands having higher average retirement ages, while others like Romania and Slovenia have lower average retirement ages. Some countries (e.g., Austria, Luxembourg, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Romania) display earlier exit times compared to statutory retirement ages. The peak distribution for exit is around 60 years for women, and 65 years for men.

Work exit routes in European countries are, as expected, for the majority of individuals in our sample, through public pension: 79% (most common reason), own ill health (8%), early retirement incentives (6%), private occupational pension (4%). Results show a significant variation in exit routes across countries: while in Germany 74% exit through public pension and 13% ill health, in Italy 89% public pension and 7% use private occupational pension. Whereas Greece and Poland show high reliance on public pension (96%), in Denmark there are more diverse exit routes.

Annex 1. Country sample sizes

Country	n	% from total
Austria	3383	4.96%
Germany	4435	6.50%
Sweden	2419	3.55%
Netherlands	2065	3.03%
Spain	2074	3.04%
Italy	3617	5.30%
France	2882	4.23%
Denmark	2334	3.42%
Greece	3094	4.54%
Switzerland	1839	2.70%
Belgium	4450	6.53%
Czech Republic	3278	4.81%
Poland	4793	7.03%
Luxembourg	809	1.19%
Hungary	1811	2.66%
Portugal	1614	2.37%
Slovenia	4405	6.46%
Estonia	4445	6.52%
Croatia	4638	6.80%
Lithuania	1405	2.06%
Bulgaria	827	1.21%
Cyprus	733	1.07%
Finland	1754	2.57%
Latvia	1684	2.47%
Malta	874	1.28%
Romania	1480	2.17%
Slovakia	1050	1.54%
Total	68192	100.0%

Part 3. Individual risk factors and exit routes, a case study of Norway

Introduction

Norway is a social-democratic welfare state associated with universalism and egalitarianism (Esping-Andersen, 1990) with a well-regulated labour market aiming to promote equality and inclusiveness. According to the Norwegian Working Environment Act, employers can dismiss employees who are 70 years old (public and state sector) and 70-72 years old (private sector) without any objective grounds. The Norwegian welfare state provides income support and benefits, mostly universal, with exception of some mean-tested, for those who are unable to work or retired, or have insufficient income. Due to population ageing and the following increase of financial costs, Norway, like many developed countries, has reformed the pension system to strengthen the incentives to work above the threshold age for early retirement. However, encouraging older workers to postpone retirement may increase inequalities as not all workers have equal opportunities to adjust their timing of exit and extending their working life, e.g. due to health issues, skills gap, and care responsibilities.

The aim of this part of the working paper is to map out how individual risk factors correlates with differences in work exit routes. Moreover, we will explore how gender in relation to differences in exit routes may shape vulnerability among elderly.

Institutional framework

The primary objective of the Norwegian pension system is to ensure that individuals maintain a reasonable income level relative to their previous earnings and accustomed standard of living. Furthermore, the pension system is designed to provide an adequate basic security for individuals who have had minimal or no engagement with the labour market.

The key element in the present pension system in Norway is based on three pillars, a universal public old-age pension from the National Insurance Scheme, second, contractual early retirement schemes, and third, occupational pension schemes in the public and private sector. In 2011 Norway introduced a reform which entailed a major restructuring of the universal old-age pension. Norway introduced a flexible retirement for the age group 62 to 75 years rather than a fixed retirement age (67 years in the old pension system). Further, the key element of the new old-age pension system is the introduction of the principle of longevity adjustment of benefits. The annual retirement benefits are life-long and will be based on the remaining life expectancy determined for the belonging cohort (Christensen et al., 2012; Hernæs et al., 2016; Kudrna, 2017; Halvorsen & West-Pedersen, 2019; West Pedersen & Schøyen, 2021). Each cohort will receive a set of separate life expectancy divisors from the age of 62 until the age of 75. If life expectancy increases, each cohort must work longer than the previous cohort to receive the same pension.

The general rule for entitlement to retirement pension is to have lived and worked in Norway for at least five years. Those who would like to draw retirement pension before the age of 67, need a pensionable income above a given minimum threshold. It is possible to combine work and retirement pension without the pension being reduced. Receiving a full retirement pension requires approximately 40 years of accumulation. Moreover, Norway has a relatively generous minimum-income protection schemes for old-age pensioners. Before the reform of the old-age pension system, the minimum pension was based on a flat-rate benefit. The calculation of the minimum-income pension is rather complex (for a detailed description see West Pedersen, 2024). The main principle is an indexation rule that links the minimum pension to developments in average wages with a deduction for increase in longevity among successive birth cohorts, as such the benefit levels are set to decline in relative terms in line with future increases in longevity.

Disability pension is an exit route for workers who need to withdraw from working life earlier than earned entitlement to retirement pension. Persons whose duration of sick leave has exceeded 52 weeks, and the state of health indicates that it is not possible to return to work, or the work capacity has been reduced by at least 50 per cent due to illness or injury, can apply for work assessment allowance. The general rule to entitlement for work assessment allowance is that the following conditions must be fulfilled: 1) the ability to work must be impaired due to illness or injury, 2) the ability to work must be impaired by at least 50 per cent, 3) the ability to work must be impaired for all types of work qualified, 4) in need for treatment to improve the ability to work or need help from Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV) to retain or find work, 5) must have been a member of the National Insurance Scheme for at least 5 years, 6) between 18 and 67 years of age. The length of time in which it is possible to receive work assessment allowance is up to 3 years. Persons with a reduced work and earning capacity due to a long-lasting illness, injury, or disability, can apply for disability benefit. The following criteria must be met: 1) between 18 and 67 years of age, 2) must have been a member of the National Insurance Scheme for at least 5 years prior long-lasting illness, injury, or disability, and 3) work or earning capacity must have been reduced by at least 50 per cent. Additionally, appropriate treatment that can improve the ability to work and vocational rehabilitation to improve the earning and work capacity must be clarified. The work assessment allowance and the disability benefit are 66 per cent of the average pensionable income in the best 3 out of the last 5 years prior to illness or disability, with a ceiling up to 6 B.A (B.A.: EUR 62 347). There are other rules for young persons with disabilities or long-lasting illness (below 26 years of age).

Individual risk factors and vulnerability among older workers

The pension reform implemented in 2011 introduced the possibility for individuals to choose the commencement of their old-age pension withdrawals from the National Insurance Scheme within the age range of 62 to 75 years. Concurrently, the withdrawal of the pension has been decoupled from the actual cessation of employment. This flexibility facilitates a distinction between the retirement decision (i.e., the decision to stop working) and the withdrawal decision (i.e., the decision to begin pension withdrawals).

This flexibility allows people to tailor their retirement plans to their personal and financial circumstances, rather than being constrained by a fixed retirement age. The separation of the retirement decision from the pension withdrawal decision means that individuals can continue

working while drawing their pension or retire without immediately starting their pension withdrawals. By allowing retirement withdrawals to start as late as 75, the reform may encourage older workers to remain in the workforce longer. This reform can positively impact individuals' financial situations by providing greater flexibility and control over retirement planning. However, it may also lead to a polarisation between those who are able to extend their working lives and those who are constrained by health issues. Consequently, individuals with the capacity to work longer can potentially enhance their financial stability, while those unable to do so may face financial disadvantages. In a Norwegian context, a study by Aakvik et al. (2024) explored the impact of health on individuals' responsiveness to economic incentives in the Norwegian pension reform. The study compared number of working hours and employment of cohorts who turned 62 before and after the 2011 pension reform. A key finding is that the effect appears to be independent of health status and applies to both male and female: those with the poorest health increased their labour supply at least as much as those with no health issues. However, the study by Aakvik et al. (2024) primarily measured the effect of the flexible withdrawal rules and not the effect of retirement benefits dependent on life expectancy adjustment. Moreover, parts of the pension reform are being gradually phased in. Thus, it will not be until 2025 that all individuals aged 62 or older will be covered by the national pension scheme and able to retire at this age.

Another Norwegian study by Grødem and Kitterød (2021) examined how men and women between 30 to 61 years old imagine their lives as pensioners. The main results indicated that approximately one-third expect working after the possible retiring age, men slightly more than women. Further, the results showed that health and income were significant factors in male's perceptions of retirement age, while partners and children are more important among females.

Data and sample

In this part of the study, we make use of the Quality-of-life Survey which is a large online national annually repeated cross-section survey carried out by Statistics Norway. The purpose of the surveys is to gain knowledge about the quality of life in the Norwegian population and shed light on differences among different groups.

Each year, a sample of 40,000 persons aged 18 years and above who were resident in Norway are drawn for the Quality-of-life Survey. Those who were drawn, received an email or letter additional to SMS with information about the survey with a link to an online form. In addition to the data collected through the online form, the study included information from a multitude of administrative registers. The register data encompassed pertinent information, such as participants' age, nationality, residential location, marital status, income, financial transfers, and occupational activity. Detailed insights into the documentation, selection procedures, questionnaire, and variables derived from the register data can be found in the documentation report corresponding to the respective years (Grimstad & Støren, 2022, 2023).

Our primary interests are to study employment among older workers and exit routs before statutory retirement age. Thus, our main sample of interest is persons between 50 and 75 years of age, which is our main selection criterion. The sample size is a clear limitation. As such, to ensure an adequate sample size, respondents from the years 2022 and 2023 were merged into one sample. We further excluded respondents without completed information on all variables of interest, and respondents with the employment status homemaker (N=81), unemployed (N=123) and other (N=166), as they are too few to be treated distinctly. Based on this, we define two overlapping samples for our analyses in which: Sample 1) persons aged between 50 and 75

years of age (N=8187); Sample 2) persons aged 50 years and above, but below the statutory retirement age at 67 years of age (N=7803). The descriptive statistics of both samples are presented in Table 1.

Variables

In this part of the working paper, we aim to describe vulnerability in old age by using different measures of health, financial situation, care responsibilities, social relationship, and investigate how such factors affect labour market attachment and exit routes.

The primary variable of interest is attachment to the labour market, which also includes exit routes. We use four outcomes of labour market attachment derived from self-defined employment status, working hours and main activity, and individual annual earnings, retirement and disability pension from administrative register data. Moreover, we use age to indicate early or late exit with a main distinction between below 67 years or above, which was the statutory retirement age before the pension reform and still is the age-threshold most of the respondents withdraw from employment. Those who are both retired and 67 years or older are excluded from the analytical samples.

The five outcomes on employment status are: 1) employed, 50 to 66 years of age, 2) employed after 66 years of age, 3) early retirement, between 62 and 66 years of age, 4) disability pension, 50 to 66 years of age.

Health

We use three measures on health, the first is related to long-lasting health problems with limitations, the second is a measure on mental health problems, and the third is self-rated general health.

Long-lasting health problems is measured by using a set of questions that was further organised into four categories. More specific, the first question used was: “Do you have any long-term illnesses or health problems that have lasted or are expected to last at least 6 months?” With the help-texts: Also include illnesses or problems that are seasonal or that come and go. With the options yes, no, will not answer/do not know. Respondents who answered *no* are defined as 1) *no health issues*. Respondent answering yes got the follow-up question: “Does any of this create limitations in carrying out normal everyday activities?”. With the options: yes, no, will not answer/do not know. Respondents who answered *no* are defined as 2) *health issues without limitations*. Respondents who answered yes got the follow-up question: “Have these limitations lasted for six months or more?”. With the options: yes, no, will not answer/do not know. Respondents answering no, are defined as 2) *health issues without limitations*. Respondents answering yes got the follow-up question: “Would you say that you experience major limitations or some limitations?”, respondents answering some limitations are defined as 3) *long-lasting health issues with some limitations*, those answering severe limitations are defined as 4) *long-lasting health issues with severe limitations*.

Mental health issues are measured by using the Hopkins Symptom Checklist (HSCL-5), which is a commonly used set of questions to screen for symptoms of anxiety and depression (Kleppang & Hagquist, 2016; Schmalbach et al., 2021). The five-item version is derived from the longer HSCL-25. The HSCL-5 includes items that are representative of core symptoms of anxiety and depression, ensuring that it captures the most critical aspects of these conditions.

All respondents were asked “Below you will find various ailments and problems that people occasionally have. How much did each problem bother you during the last 14 days?” 1) Feeling fearful, 2) Nervousness or shakiness inside, 3) Feeling hopeless about the future, 4) Feeling blue, 5) Worrying too much about things. The respondents rated each item on a four-point Likert scale, ranging from not at all to extremely. The total score is calculated by summing the responses where high scores indicating greater level of mental health problems. Respondents with a score above 2, are defined as having mental health issues and got the value 1, otherwise 0.

Self-rated poor health is based on a question which is a commonly used in the literature and is considered as a valid and reliable measure of general health (Idler & Benyamini, 1997; Farmer & Ferraro, 1997; Dumas et al., 2020). All respondents were asked, “How will you rate your health in general?” With the options very good, good, neither good nor bad, poor, very poor. For ease of modelling, we recoded the original five levels into a binary variable. Those individuals whose value is poor or very poor, are defined as *having poor health* and got the value 1, otherwise 0.

Financial situation

We use three different measures to capture the financial situation, the first is income poverty, the second is difficulties in making ends meet, and the third is future financial insecurity. All measures refer to the financial situation within households.

Income poverty (at-risk-of-poverty) is calculated by using information about the respondents' income, which is obtained from Statistics Norway's income and asset register for households and was merged after the data collection was completed. We follow the harmonised EU standard and define a household as income poor if the net equivalised disposable income after social transfers is below 60% of the median net equivalised income of the population.

Difficulties in making ends meet refers to self-reported ability of households to cover their basic living expenses with their current income. All respondents were asked: “Think about your total income/ total income of everyone in your household. How easy or difficult is it for you/you all to make ends meet with this income on a daily basis?”. With the options very difficult, difficult, fairly difficult, fairly easy, easy, very easy. For ease of modelling, we recoded the original six levels into two different measures. The first is a dummy where individuals whose value is very difficult or difficult are valued 1, otherwise 0. The second is organised in three categories, “very difficult” and “difficult” are defined as difficult, and “fairly difficult” and “fairly easy” are defined as *somewhat difficult*, and “easy” and “very easy” are defined as *easy*.

Future financial insecurity refers to self-reported concern for the financial situation in the future. All respondents were asked: “To what extent do you worry about your future financial situation?”. With the options not worried at all, somehow worried, quite worried, very worried. For ease of modelling, we recoded the original four levels into a binary variable. Those individuals whose value is quite worried or very worried, are defined as experiencing future financial insecurity and are valued 1, otherwise 0.

Care responsibilities

All respondents were questioned about various life events, those who reported having care responsibilities for a close family member within the past five years are defined as having care responsibilities and are valued 1, otherwise 0.

Working conditions

Characteristics of the work situation or work environment are captured by six variables related to well-established measures of job quality, job security, and the psychosocial work environment (Kristensen et al., 2005; Lewcuk, 2017; Vives et al., 2010). The following provides a description of the variables used in the descriptive analyses.

Low satisfaction with job is based on a question given to all respondents who were employed. They were asked to rate their satisfaction on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 indicates not satisfied at all and 10 indicates very satisfied. The scores are often categorised into three based on scores between 0 and 5 indicate low satisfaction, 6 to 8 indicate moderate satisfaction, and 9 to 10 indicate high satisfaction (cf. Støren et al., 2020). For easy modelling, we use a dummy on low satisfaction were scores between 0 and 5 are valued 1, otherwise 0.

Low degree of autonomy in work includes individuals who answered, “to a very small extent” or “to a small extent” to the question “To what extent can you influence decisions that are important for your work?” (to a very large extent / to a large extent / to some extent / to a small extent / to a very small extent).

Low flexibility in the job includes individuals who answered, “a quarter of the time” or “rarely or never” to the question “Can you decide when to take breaks from work?” (all or almost all the time / about three-quarters of the time / half the time / a quarter of the time / rarely or never).

Skills mismatch includes individuals who answered “poor” or “very poor” to the question “How are the opportunities in your job to utilize the skills, knowledge, and experience you have gained through education and work?” (very good / good / neither good nor poor / poor / very poor).

Autonomy, flexibility and possibilities to utilize own skills at work are generally important for a good working environment and can be crucial for prolonging employment of older workers, in particular among those with long-term health problems, to be able to work satisfactorily without compromising their health.

Mentally exhausted after work includes individuals who answered that they “daily” or “a couple of days a week” felt mentally exhausted when they came home from work. The original response categories were “daily”, “a couple of days a week”, “about once a week”, “a couple of times a month”, and “rarely or never”.

Physically exhausted after work includes individuals who answered that they “daily” or “a couple of days a week” felt physically exhausted when they came home from work. The original response categories were “daily”, “a couple of days a week”, “about once a week”, “a couple of times a month”, and “rarely or never”.

Loneliness and social relations

Earlier research indicate that social relationships are essential for health outcomes, such as physical and mental health, and cognitive functioning (Fratiglioni, Paillard-Borg, & Winblad, 2004; Wang et al., 2023). There exists a diversity in the instruments designed to assess the perceived deficit of social relations, commonly termed as loneliness, and the actual deficit of social relations, often referred to as social isolation (See e.g. Aartsen et al., 2024). In this study, we use one measure on loneliness and two measures on social relations, additional to living with a partner.

Loneliness is derived from a direct question about loneliness, which was included together with a set of questions related to illness and issues. All respondents were asked "Below, you will find various illnesses and issues that one might occasionally experience. How much has each problem troubled or bothered you over the past 14 days? Among these categories, "feeling of loneliness" was one of the aspects to be evaluated on a four-point Likert scale, ranging from "not at all" to "very much." Loneliness is dichotomised, with individuals who reported feeling lonely "quite often" or "very often" being categorised with a value of 1 (indicating loneliness), otherwise 0. We acknowledge that direct questions about loneliness may lead to an underestimation of its prevalence, as openly admitting to feelings of loneliness can be stigmatising, even in anonymous surveys (Surkalim et al., 2022).

Social relations, specified as **rarely spending time with friends or rarely spending time with family**, are assessed based on two questions: one concerning time spent with friends, "How often do you spend time with good friends? Do not include members of your own family," and another regarding time spent with family, "How often do you spend time with family members? Do not include those you live with." The response categories are "daily", "weekly, but not daily", "Monthly, but not weekly", "A few times a year", "Less often", "I have no close friends/family". Respondents reporting the three last categories are defined as rarely spending time with friends or family.

Living with a partner is based on the question "Do you live with someone?" and coded living with a partner yes (0) or no (1).

Discriminated against

Two measures of self-reported discrimination are included, based on the question: "In the past 12 months, have you experienced being treated worse than others because of...?" This question encompasses a range of possible categories. Individuals who reported being treated worse due to health problems, illness, or disability were recoded into a single dichotomous variable indicating discriminated against due to health or disability (1) (originally two separate categories), otherwise 0. And, discriminated against due to age (1), otherwise 0. A limitation of these questions is that they do not specify the circumstances under which the discrimination occurred.

Individual characteristics

Information on gender were collected from register data and categorised as male (0) and **female** (1). Information about highest level of **education** completed is collected from register data and includes four categories including primary and lower secondary education, upper secondary education, bachelor's degree, and master's degree or higher. These four categories were for simplicity recoded into higher education (1) and lower education (0).

Descriptive statistics

In this section, we will present descriptive statistics of the total sample, including both sample 1 and sample 2 to explore whether those who continue working beyond the age of 67 represent a more advantaged segment of the population in terms of health, educational attainment, working conditions, and financial situation. By investigating these dimensions, we aim to shed light on the potential disparities and advantages that may exist within the labour market for older workers.

The analytical sample consists of persons who are employed and further categorised into three age groups: 50 to 61 years (N=6314), 62 to 66 years (N=1489), and 67 to 75 years (N=384). Table 1. provides an overview of various dimensions among older workers across the three age groups: 50-61, 62-66, and 67-75 and covers aspects such as individual characteristics, working environment and job satisfaction, health and social relations.

The primary observations indicate that the gender balance in employment among older workers aged 50 to 61 nearly equal, with women constituting 48.7% of this workforce. However, in subsequent age cohorts, the proportion of employed men exceeds that of employed women. This disparity is particularly pronounced in the oldest age group, where women represent only 31.8% of the employed population. These findings highlight the gendered disparities in labour force participation, which become more apparent as age increases.

The percentage of older workers with higher education is relatively large and stable in all age groups, ranging from 48.6% (50-61 years), 44.5% (62-66 years) and 51.6% (67-75 years). Workers in the oldest age group are less likely to have given care to a relative during the last five years (6%) compared to the younger age groups where approximately 10% report such care responsibilities.

The working environment may be important in providing opportunities and encouraging older workers to continue working beyond the age of 67. Main findings indicate that the youngest age group reports lower job satisfaction (37.7%) compared to workers aged 62 to 66 (29.2%) and compared to the oldest age group (21.2%). Furthermore, skill mismatch is more prevalent among the youngest age group (19.4%) compared to 16.0% in the 62-66 age group and 10.7% in the oldest age group. Another pattern emerges concerning workplace flexibility and autonomy in work. The differences between the two younger age groups (50-61 and 62-66) are relatively similar regarding flexibility (27.4% and 25.8%) and autonomy (12.4% and 12.9%), whereas the oldest age group reports significantly lower levels of low flexibility (14.0%) and low autonomy (7.1%). Furthermore, measures used to assess the psychosocial work environment reveal that the oldest age group is less likely to feel mentally (5.2%) or physically (12.0%) exhausted after work compared to 15.3% (mentally) and 22.1% (physically) in the 62-66 age group, and 23.3% (mentally) and 28.2% (physically) in the 50-61 age group.

Working in old age, particularly beyond the statutory age, may be motivated by the need to improve one's financial situation. Although our study is not designed to differentiate the reasons for working beyond the statutory age, the question of whether respondents are concerned about their future economic situation may indicate that continued employment among those aged 67-75 is aimed at improving their financial circumstances. The results indicate that a relatively small percentage of individuals in the oldest age group (5.2%) express concern about their future economic situation. However, the proportions for the younger age groups, 62-66 at 7.3% and 50-61 at 10.2% respectively, are not significantly higher. On the other hand, there are more pronounced differences between the age groups regarding their ability to make ends meet. 14.6% of workers aged 50 to 61 reported difficulties in making ends meet, which is significant higher compared to workers aged 62 to 66 (7.8%) and workers aged 67 to 75 (5.0%). The risk of poverty is low across all age groups, with respective percentages of 2.3% (50-61 years), 2.2% (62-66 years) and 1.3% (67-75 years).

	Age groups			N
	50-61	62-66	67-75	
Female	48.7	43.7	31.8	3845
Higher education	48.6	44.5	51.6	3932
Care responsibility last 5 years	10.3	10.9	6.0	837
Low satisfaction with job	37.7	29.2	21.2	2875
Low flexibility at work	27.4	25.8	14.0	1934
Skills mismatch	19.4	16.0	10.7	1495
Low degree of autonomy in work	12.4	12.9	7.1	898
Mentally exhausted after work	23.3	15.3	5.2	1699
Physically exhausted after work	28.2	22.1	12.0	2138
Concerned about future economic situation	10.2	7.3	5.2	771
Difficulty in making ends meet	14.6	7.8	5.0	1055
At-risk-of-poverty	2.3	2.2	1.3	181
Long lasting health problems with limitations	48.2	49.0	51.3	3970
Mental health issues	11.6	7.5	6.0	870
Loneliness	6.6	4.4	2.3	494
Rarely spending time with friends	23.2	22.8	18.8	1878
Rarely spending time with family	20.5	16.5	14.8	1593
Lives without a partner	22.3	24.1	20.3	2843
Discriminated against due to health or disability	5.0	2.7	2.3	363
Discriminated against due to age	6.0	7.5	7.8	522
Total number of respondents	6314	1489	384	8187

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of older workers – sample persons in the age group 50 to 75. Percent and number of respondents. Data: Quality of Life Survey 2022 and 2023. Norway.

Few of all age groups reported loneliness and the majority had regular contact with family or friends and close to 8 of 10 individuals lives with a partner. The percentage of respondents reporting loneliness was 6.6% in the age group 50-61, followed by 4.4% (age group 62-66) and 2.3% (age group 67-75). The percentage of individuals who reported less frequent contact with friends is rather similar between the age groups, 23.2% (50-61 years), 22.8% (62-66 years) and 18.8% (67-75 years). Furthermore, the youngest age group had a higher percentage of individuals (20.5%) who reported less frequent contact with family compared to workers aged 62-66 (16.5%) and workers aged 67-75 (14.8%).

Nearly half of the individuals reported that they had experienced long-lasting health problems with some or severe limitations. Moreover, the majority of respondents are not defined as having mental health issues according to the HSCL-5. Notably, the prevalence of reported mental health issues is highest among workers aged 50-61 (11.6%), followed by those aged 62-66 (7.5%), and those aged 67-75 (6.0%). It is important to note that the health measures are broadly defined and encompass health issues that may have minimal or no impact on the ability to work.

The frequency of health or disability discrimination, as well as age discrimination, was reported by a minority of respondents across all age groups. Discrimination based on health or disability was more frequently reported among workers aged 50-61 (5%), followed by 2.7% in the 62-66 age group and 2.3% in the 67-75 age group. Conversely, age discrimination was slightly more prevalent among the older cohorts, 7.8% and 7.5% in the oldest age groups, compared to 6.0% in the youngest age group.

Summary

The descriptive analyses suggest that workers aged 67 to 75 who remain in the workforce tend to exhibit better health, higher educational attainment, greater job satisfaction, stronger financial stability, and more active social lives. This positive selection indicates that those who continue working beyond the statutory retirement age are generally more advantaged in various aspects of their lives. Conversely, our findings indicate that the youngest age group (50-61 years) faces several significant challenges compared to their older counterparts. They report the lowest levels of job satisfaction, the highest prevalence of skill mismatch, and the greatest levels of mental and physical exhaustion after work. Furthermore, financial concerns are more prominent among this group, expressing worry about their future economic situation and reporting more often difficulties in making ends meet. Thus, in a Norwegian context, our results suggest that those aged 67 to 75 do not delay their exit from the workforce due to financial necessity. This may indicate a positive selection of older people with good health and favourable working conditions.

Exit routes

We will explore the differences between persons who are defined as employed, early retirees and those receiving disability pension. The analyses are based on sample 2 excluding persons who are retired at the statutory retirement age of 67 and persons older than 67 who are employed. Additional analyses show that including those who are employed after 67 does not alter the substantial results regarding the employed group.

To better understand the differences in terms of vulnerabilities between these groups, we are estimating multinomial logistic regressions. The reference category are persons who are employed. Hence, the results will indicate whether the likelihood of early retirement or respectively disability pension varies accordingly to different individual-level factors compared to those who are employed. The results are presented as average marginal effects, instead of odds ratios. Odds ratios compare the odds of occurrence of an event relative to its non-occurrence, without offering guidance on the magnitude of this likelihood. Average marginal effects on the other hand measure the change in probability of an event for a unit change in the predictor variable, thus allowing us to more directly comment on the magnitude of the associations we estimate. All regression models employ robust standard errors to account for potential heterogeneity and include controls for gender, age, marital status/living alone,

economic vulnerability indicators, care responsibilities, contact with friends and family, as well as health status as previously described. Additionally, we conduct separate analyses for women and men to illustrate how each factor influences exit routes for both genders, thereby incorporating implicit interactions between all variables and gender. Before presenting the regression results, we outline some of the key descriptive findings.

Descriptive findings for exit routes

Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for individuals under 67 who have exited the workforce through employment, early retirement, or disability pension. The majority (76.3%) remained employed, while 7.1% took early retirement, and 16.6% exited via disability pension.

	Exit routes			
	Employed (N=7803)	Early retirement (N=730)	Disability pension (N=1693)	Total (N=10226)
Group's percentage	76.3%	7.1%	16.6%	100.0%
Age, in years (mean, standard deviation)	56.8 (4.54)	64.5 (1.45)	58.8 (4.89)	57.7 (4.90)
Sex				
Male	52.3%	50.1%	37.6%	49.7%
Female	47.7%	49.9%	62.4%	50.3%
Higher education	47.9%	36.4%	24.6%	43.2%
Self-reported poor health	6.1%	4.1%	43.9%	12.2%
Mental health issues (HSCL-5)	10.9%	5.6%	34.0%	14.3%
Long-lasting health problems				
No health issues	51.6%	41.9%	7.3%	43.6%
Health issue without limitations	26.2%	36.6%	12.8%	24.7%
Health issues, some limitations	17.8%	19.0%	40.4%	21.6%
Health issues, severe limitations	4.3%	2.5%	39.6%	10.0%

Discriminated due to age	6.3%	4.8%	8.7%	6.6%
Discriminated due to health	4.5%	3.7%	24.9%	7.8%
Difficulty in making ends meet				
Difficult	4.5%	3.3%	21.7%	7.3%
Somewhat difficult	8.7%	6.0%	20.4%	10.5%
Easy	86.7%	90.7%	57.9%	82.2%
Household income below 60% of median income				
At-risk-of-poverty	2.3%	2.7%	12.1%	3.9%
Concerned about future economic situation				
Concerned	9.6%	6.0%	30.2%	12.8%
Lives with a partner: No	18.2%	20.7%	32.3%	20.9%
Has had care burden during the past 5 years: Yes	10.4%	11.0%	13.1%	10.9%
Reporting feeling lonely: yes	6.2%	4.0%	18.0%	8.0%
Together with friends: rarely (new)	19.5%	16.9%	26.6%	20.6%
Together with friends: rarely (new)	22.9%	23.6%	30.4%	24.3%

Table 2 Descriptive statistics - exit routes – sample persons under 67 years of age. Data: Quality of Life Survey 2022 & 2023. Norway.

The average age varied across exit routes, with early retirees being the oldest. The gender distribution was almost equal in the employed and early retirement groups, but women constituted the majority in the disability pension group (62.4%). Most individuals in all groups

did not have higher education, with the highest percentage among those in the disability pension group, namely (75%). These results are in line with existing findings. For instance, a study by Bruusgaard and colleagues (2010) found a significant association between lower educational attainment and the likelihood of receiving a disability pension. The study highlighted that individuals with fewer years of education were more likely to be granted a disability pension (Bruusgaard, Smeby, & Claussen, 2010; Rubio Valverde et al., 2022). Moreover, a study that investigating changes over time in the expected years of good health above and below pension age by education level in the Netherlands, finds that individual with lower educational attainment was more likely to experience health deficits, which can contribute to higher rates of disability pension (Valverde et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the nature of the data does not allow us to conclude whether persons in disability pension group have had long-lasting health issues that impeded them in taking higher education, or whether lower education as such directly influences the likelihood of being on disability pension in Norway.

The majority of respondents did not report poor health or mental health issues. However, a significant portion of the disability pension group reported poor health and mental health issues (34%). Overall, the share who report health issues is lowest in the employed group, somewhat higher in the early retirement group and substantial in the disability pension group.

For the question regarding financial ease or difficulty, a vast majority in the employed (86.7%) and early retirement (90.7%) groups found it easy to manage their finances, whereas only 57.9% of those on disability pension reported the same. Furthermore, the disability pension group had the highest proportion (12.1%) of individuals at risk of poverty (60% of the median income), compared to only 2.3% in the employed and 2.7% in the early retirement groups. Lastly, around one third of the persons in the disability pension group (30.2%) showed the most concern about their future financial situation, while such concern was significantly less in the employed (9.6%) and early retirement (6.0%) groups. These results suggest that individuals in the disability pension group face more financial difficulties and concerns compared to those in the employed and early retirement groups.

A small percentage in each group reported experiencing age discrimination, with the highest incidence in the disability pension group (8.7%). Health discrimination was also reported, with the highest prevalence again in the disability pension group (24.9%). This suggests that individuals in the disability pension group potentially face more discrimination based on age and health compared to those in the employed and early retirement group.

The disability pension group has the highest percentage of individuals who do not live with a partner (32.3%), followed by early retired (20.7%) and employed (18.2%). Regarding social aspects, the majority in all groups did not report feeling lonely. However, a significantly higher percentage of individuals in the disability pension group (18.0%) reported feelings of loneliness compared to those in the employed (6.2%) and early retirement (4.0%) groups. Furthermore, most individuals across all groups reported having regular contact with good friends and family. However, the disability pension group again showed a higher percentage of individuals (30.4%) who reported less frequent contact with friends compared to those in the employed (22.9%) and early retirement (23.6%) groups. Similarly, in terms of contact with family, a higher share of persons on disability pension report having rarely contact with friends (26.65), compared to persons who are employed (19.5%) or on early retirement (16.9%).

Around one out of ten individuals in all groups have had caring obligations in the past five years. However, there is a slightly higher proportion of individuals with caregiving obligations amongst those receiving disability pension.

Regression results – exit routes

The results from the regression analyses will be presented sequentially, first focusing on the differences between those employed and those who retired early, thereafter between those who are employed and those on disability pension. The models are estimated separately for women and men. All the results presented indicate correlations; the relationship between control variables and outcome measures does not indicate any causal direction. This means that measures of, for example, mental health problems may be caused by being a recipient of disability benefits and not as a basis for receiving disability pension. The variance inflation factor scores are low (between 1.1 and 1.3) in the estimated models, showing that multicollinearity is not of concern here.

Figure 1. shows the estimates for early retirement, disability versus being in employment for women, while figure 2. presents these estimates for men. The results are presented as average marginal effects. The analyses for women contain data from 5 111 individuals, while the models for men contain data from 5 067 individuals, after missing observations were removed. The proportion of missing is very low in these data and totals 48 observations. We emphasize that these results present associations between various measures of vulnerability and do not present causal estimates of the impact of each factor.

Health limitations show mixed associations with the likelihood of early retirement. Having some health issues without limitations or health issues with some limitations increases the probability of early retirement, with only the former being statistically significant. Severe health limitations do not significantly affect the likelihood of early retirement. This latter result might be because persons with severe health limitations either receive long-term sick leave and thereafter disability benefits, or a full pension, rather than early retirement.

Women who have experienced age discrimination are less likely to be in the early retirement group compared to being in employment. Health discrimination is not statistically significant. Furthermore, contrasted to being in employment we do not find that women who have experienced financial difficulty have a higher likelihood of being in early retirement. We do not find statistically significant associations for being concerned about one's future economic situation and early retirement. Additionally, women who are in the early retirement group are as likely as women who are employed to experience loneliness and have as much contact with friends. Nevertheless, we find that women who do not have a partner are less likely to be in early retirement compared to employment. Lastly, age is a positive and statistically significant predictor of early retirement, however having higher education decreases the probability of early retirement, but this association is not statistically significant at the 5% level for women.

Women only. Reference category: employed. N = 5,111

Figure 1 Exit routes for women. Average marginal effects based on multinomial logistic regressions estimated on the sample of women. Data: Quality-of-life Survey 2022 and 2023. Norway.

The right panel of figure 1 shows the likelihood of being on disability pensions versus employment for women, while the left panel shows being on disability pension versus being in employment for women.

The results show that women receiving disability benefits are more likely to experience both physical and mental health issues. Women with reported mental health issues are more likely to be on disability pension. Health limitations have a significant association with the likelihood of being on disability pension. The magnitude of this association increases with the severity of health limitations. These results show that women with health issues and health limitations are more likely to receive disability benefits than be in employment. Our findings show a strong correlation between receiving disability benefits and mental health problems for women, even though milder mental health issues are not sufficient to qualify for disability benefits in Norway. This suggests that female disability benefit recipients are in a particularly vulnerable situation.

Furthermore, women who experienced discrimination due to health are more likely to be on disability benefits than in employment. Additionally, the prevalence of age discrimination is lower among women on disability pensions compared to those who are employed. We do not find any significant differences in the frequency of contact with friends or family across the three groups.

Financial difficulty significantly impacts the likelihood of being on disability pension. Those who find it somewhat difficult or easy to manage finances are less likely to be on disability pension compared to those who find it very difficult.

Concern about future economic situation, living with another person (having a partner), caregiving burden, and feelings of loneliness do not significantly affect the likelihood of being on disability pension among women in these models. This might be because we still have relatively small sample sizes, and additionally our models do suffer for endogeneity issues, which

may explain why only some of the indicators for economic wellbeing and social contact are statically significant. Age has a positive and highly significant association with being on disability pension, indicating that for each additional year of age, the probability of being on disability pension increases, holding all other variables constant. Women with higher education are considerably less likely to be on disability pension compared to being in employment.

Men only. Reference category: employed. N = 5,067

Figure 2 Exit routes for men. Average marginal effects based on multinomial logistic regressions estimated on the sample of men. Data: Quality-of-life Survey 2022 and 2023. Norway.

Figure 2. presents the results for men. We will start by presenting the results of being in early retirement compared with being in employment (left panel).

It is interesting to note that neither the mental health indicator, nor the indicator of health limitations, are significantly related with being in early retirement. These results suggest that men who are early retired are as healthy as men who are employed. In contrast, our results indicated that women with health issues and limitations (some or severe limitations) were more likely to be in the early retirement, rather than in employment.

Experiencing age discrimination or health discrimination are not significantly correlated with early retirement among men. These results suggest that men who are employed and those who are early retired experience the same level of age or health discrimination.

Financial difficulties are significantly correlated with early retirement. Individuals in the early retirement group are more likely to find it very difficult to manage finances, compared to those who find it somewhat difficult or easy, with the former being statistically significant. Furthermore, men in the early retirement group are less likely to report concerns about the future economic situation compared to men in the employment group. It is interesting to note that this relationship is not observed for women, which may suggest that their decision to retire early is less dependent on their financial situation.

Having a partner, having caregiving obligations, feelings of loneliness, and frequency of contact with friends or family are not significantly associated to the likelihood of being in the early retirement group among men. However, while this result is not statistically significant there might be tendency for men in early retirement to report higher loneliness than those employed. Overall, these results suggest that men in early retirement have similar levels on these variables as men who are employed. As for women, the results indicate that being older is associated with a higher likelihood of being on early retirement, compared to remaining in employment – all else constant. However, having higher education is related with a lower probability of being in the early retirement group, suggesting that men with higher education are less likely to retire early and more likely to be in employment.

When exploring the differences between men who are on disability pension contrasted to those who are employed, we find some interesting patterns. One such result is that men who reported mental health issues are more likely to be on disability pensions compared to being in employment. As expected, health limitations have a significant and positive correlation with the likelihood of being on disability pension, compared to remaining in employment. The magnitude of this association increases with the severity of health limitations. We note that both in terms of mental health and health issues and limitations, both men and women who are in employment tend to report less health issues, compared to those on disability pension.

We also find that men who are on disability benefits are less likely to have experienced discrimination due to age, but more likely to have experienced discrimination due to health compared to men who are employed. This pattern is highly similar to the one we found for women.

For men, the results indicate that those who find it easy to make ends meet are less likely to be on disability benefits. The results suggest that men on disability benefits face greater economic concerns, particularly their ability of making ends meet. On the other hand, they are not more concerned about their future economic situation compared to employed men. This may be due to the fact that receiving disability pension, under Norwegian conditions, provides a stable and predictable income. These results are similar with the patterns observed among women.

Living with a partner, caregiving obligations, feelings of loneliness, and frequency of contact with friends do not significantly affect the likelihood of being on disability pension among men. In other words, the levels of these variables are similar for those employed and those who are receiving disability benefits.

In terms of age, we find a similar pattern as we did for women, namely that the probability of being on disability pension increases with age. These results suggest that for both men and women, those who are employed are comparatively younger, to those on disability benefits and in early retirement. Having higher education is linked with a reduced probability of being on disability pension, suggesting that men with higher education are less likely to be on disability pension and more likely to be employed. This is a pattern is also observed among women.

Robustness analyses for exit routes

Our data includes multiple indicators of economic hardship. To ascertain whether our findings are influenced by the specific indicators used, we performed further analyses using different measures of economic hardship. One such measure was the risk of poverty, defined as a household income below 60% of the median income. The results from these additional analyses aligned with the findings presented here. They revealed that both men and women receiving disability benefits have a higher propensity to be at risk of poverty compared to their employed

counterparts or those who have taken early retirement. We found no substantial differences in the risk of poverty between individuals who are employed and those who have opted for early retirement.

In additional models, we have employed the self-reported health variable instead of differentiating between health limitation and mental health issues. These results show a similar, but less detailed pattern to the ones presented above, in Figures 1 and 2. In short, it is mainly persons (both men and women) on disability pension who report poor health, while persons in employment and in early retirement are less likely to report poor health. There is a concern that meeting friends, family, and loneliness may be correlated, potentially leading our models to underestimate their impact when included together. When considering only the indicator for meeting friends, results show that women on disability pensions have less frequent contact with friends compared to employed women. Otherwise, findings for both men and women remain robust.

Lastly, we examined the impact of age on our results. We simplified the age categories into two groups: those below 62 years and those 62 years and above. We found that, for both men and women, the results were consistent with the findings we presented earlier.

Summary

The focus in this section of the working paper is to examine the differences in health, financial condition, and social relationships among three groups: employed individuals, early retirees, and those on disability pensions. The findings indicate that the employed group reports the fewest health issues, while the disability pension group reports the most. There is a strong correlation between receiving disability benefits and mental health problems, particularly among women. In terms of financial management, a majority of the employed and early retirees find it easy to manage their finances. In contrast, men and women on disability pension more frequently report difficulties in making ends meet. This group also has the highest risk of poverty. Socially, feelings of loneliness are more prevalent in the disability pension group, which also reports less frequent contact with friends and family. Overall, the findings highlight the vulnerability of individuals on disability pensions, particularly in terms of health, financial challenges, and social relationships.

Concluding remarks

The aim of this working paper was to understand the role of individual factors such as gender, health issues, care responsibilities, and financial condition in the timing of exit and work exit routes of older workers in European countries. We first provided an overview of recent research on individual and contextual factors influencing the exit from the labour market, with a focus on circumstances at individual level. Second, based on SHARE data, we investigated how gender, health, care responsibilities and income affect older workers' intentions to retire, and their work exit routes. Finally, we considered the Norwegian case and looked in depth at how individual risk factors correlate with differences in timing of exit and work exit routes.

During the past decades, policy interventions have successfully extended working lives across the continent. However, significant challenges and inequalities persist in the time of exit and exit routes of older workers. Our study contributes with new insight into overlapping dimensions of vulnerability among older workers in Europe.

In terms of gender, our results based on SHARE data showed that men and women display similar early retirement intentions. Results might reflect the increasing participation of women in the labour force over past decades and a certain shift away from traditional roles and expectations towards more similar aspirations to men in terms of transition into retirement. It is also possible that, given women's more fragmented employment trajectories and lower wages across working life in comparison to men, women's decisions for exit to be closely tied to financial considerations. Only when more individual risk factors like health limitations, financial strain and care responsibilities are taken into consideration, women tend to express early retirement intentions to a higher extent than men. Decisions of early retirement vary by gender only when individual risk factors overlap, likely conducting for women to an early exit from the labour market.

In addition to gender, other factors—such as health, financial security, caregiving roles, and workplace conditions—remain critical to understanding the complexities of retirement exit for both men and women. Health limitations constitute a key driver of early labour market exit, with poor health significantly increasing the likelihood of retirement. Care responsibilities, particularly informal care within families, present a significant challenge to extended working lives, especially for women. Financial strain also plays a crucial role in shaping retirement experiences and timing as low-income individuals often face the difficult choice between continuing to work for financial necessity and retiring with inadequate resources. Furthermore, working conditions were proven to have a significant role in shaping the exit from the labour market.

Our results based on the Norwegian Quality-of-life Survey 2022 and 2023 are mostly consistent with the findings using SHARE. However, some interesting results differ from other European countries and underscores contextual factors affecting exit from work. First, there is primarily a positive selection of persons working above the statutory age (67-75) who tend to exhibit better health, higher educational attainment, greater job satisfaction, stronger financial stability, and more active social lives. This positive selection indicates that those who remain in work are generally more advantaged in various aspects of their lives. Conversely, our findings indicate that workers in the age group 50 to 61 faces several significant challenges compared to their older counterparts. They report the lowest levels of job satisfaction, the highest prevalence of skill mismatch, and the greatest levels of mental and physical exhaustion after work. Furthermore, financial concerns are more prominent among this group, expressing worry about their future economic situation and reporting more often difficulties in making ends meet. Thus,

our results suggest that those aged 67 to 75 do not delay their exit from the workforce due to financial necessity, as found to be more prominent in other European countries. Second, it is a significant concern for Norway that a substantial portion of the working-age population exits the labour market due to disability pension or early retirement, resulting in a depletion of the workforce. The probability of being on disability pension increases with age, but more for women than men. This may be explained by generous welfare provisions for persons who, for various reasons, are not employed. This may be explained by structural factors related to the design of the pension system and income security for persons at the lower end of the income scale.

Based on previous research and our findings, additive and overlapping dimensions of vulnerability among older workers are found. By grouping factors into “pillars” of vulnerability, we can better understand the different types of challenges faced by elderly individuals who are working, or who have retired and potentially develop targeted interventions to address these vulnerabilities.

The first “pillar” is related to **health vulnerabilities**. Older persons reporting poor health, particularly chronic conditions, are more prone to be on disability pension or early retirement. A correlation between poor health and disability is expected. However, it is more concerning that there is a clear association between health issues and economic vulnerability. Older persons with poorer health are often more concerned about their future economic situation. Moreover, our findings indicate that workers who face significant health challenges, report the highest levels of mental and physical exhaustion after work and express more frequent worries about their future economic situation. They also report more difficulties in making ends meet. This implies that poor health is associated with unfavourable working conditions and greater financial concerns or economic insecurity among older workers. This implies that targeted measures which can create health-promoting workplaces could be beneficial for enabling older workers to remain in employment longer and reduce their economic vulnerability.

The second “pillar” is related to **economic vulnerability** as economic constraints influence both the intention to retire and the timing of retirement. Older workers with low income are more likely to either extend their employment or retire early with insufficient resources. In contrast, older workers with financial stability tend to have greater control over their retirement timing, often postponing retirement due to good health and favourable working conditions. This presents a future challenge because many older workers with lower education and income levels do not have a choice regarding their retirement timing. This issue will become increasingly important in the future as pension reforms eliminating a clear statutory retirement age and making income security more dependent on the duration of one's ability to work. Furthermore, there is a clear correlation between poor health and disability, which is more prevalent among women. Disability benefits are associated with financial insecurity, thereby creating a gender disparity that disadvantages women. Thus, the socio-economic dimensions will create greater disparities between elderly based on health, educational attainment, and type of job, potentially affecting women more than men.

The third “pillar” is related to **caregiver vulnerability** as informal care, particularly for women, presents a significant challenge to extended working lives. Older women's intention or decisions to retire early are more often influenced by caregiving responsibilities than those of men. This comes along with lower retirement savings due to fragmented employment trajectories and lower earnings, leading to financial gender gaps and financial insecurity in older age. This can result in women being more economically vulnerable than men in retirement. There exist some arrangements that provide caregiving leave for taking care of elderly family members or close

relatives, but this leave is not always paid and often depends on the employer's policy and collective agreement. Implementing paid leave when taking care of older relatives can provide caregivers the opportunity to take time off work without losing income, thereby reducing financial stress and allowing better balance between caregiving duties and employment. Flexible work arrangement can help caregivers manage both their work and caregiving responsibilities. On the other hand, flexibility can also have unintended effects, such as difficulties in handling the combination of work and caregiving responsibilities, which can, in turn, lead to poorer health and work-family conflict (Koreshi & Alpass, 2023).

Our findings provide new insights into how gender, health, caregiving responsibilities, and working conditions overlap and shape vulnerability. However, some limitations must be acknowledged. First, our analyses are based on cross-sectional data. Thus, we cannot determine causality, but only the relationships between individual factors, such as health, material resources, and care burden on outcome measures such as intention to retire and exit routes. Second, the low number of respondents imposes clear limitations on our choice of analyses. It significantly restricts the subgroups we can study and the possibilities of examining the intersection of key individual characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, and caregiving responsibilities. Additionally, there are limitations regarding the inclusion of both contextual and individual factors by using multilevel analyses.

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